

ANALYSIS OF THE ONSET OF TRANSONIC BUFFET IN A CIVIL FAN BLADE

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the onset of transonic buffet in large civil fan blades numerically. As fan blades are designed to be longer and more flexible to meet increasing efficiency demands, they become more susceptible to aerodynamic instabilities. One such instability, transonic buffet, is characterised by unsteady shock wave–boundary layer interactions (SWBLI) that can induce periodic shock motion and potential structural vibrations. Using the in-house unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (URANS) solver AU3D, this work analyses the shock movement behaviour on a civil fan blade, where high-speed aeroelastic instability was observed experimentally. A range of operating conditions is simulated, revealing distinct regimes of shock behaviour. Buffet here is identified around the design speed of the fan at flow rates greater than those for peak efficiency. Particular attention is given to identifying the onset of buffet and examining its dominant frequency and modal forcing characteristics. This paper aims to provide deeper understanding into the underlying mechanisms of shock buffet in civil fan blades.

Keywords: Unsteady Aerodynamics, Shock Wave–Boundary–Layer Interactions (SWBLIs), Transonic Buffet, Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes Method (URANS), Fan Blade

NOMENCLATURE

a speed of sound
 c chord
 f_b buffet frequency
 Ma Mach number
 Ma_c local Mach number
 y^+ non-dimensionalised wall distance
 C_p surface pressure coefficient

C_p' unsteady pressure coefficient
 \bar{p} time-averaged pressure
 p' unsteady pressure
 $p_{0,\infty}$ free-stream total pressure
 p_∞ free-stream static pressure
 R correlation coefficient
OP operating point
SWBLI shock wave–boundary layer interaction
URANS unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the last few decades, increasing demand for improved fuel efficiency and reduced emissions in civil aviation has driven continuous advancements in aero-engine technology. Such shift has led to the development of fan blades that are larger, more lightweight, and aerodynamically refined to meet performance and efficiency demands. These modern blades are often made from composite materials and operating at transonic flow conditions, they are inherently more flexible and thus more susceptible to the complex unsteady aerodynamic phenomena at transonic regime. While such designs contribute to improved propulsion efficiency, they also introduce challenges related to aerodynamic and aeroelastic stability.

One important phenomenon that arises in the transonic regime is transonic buffet—an unsteady shock wave–boundary layer interaction (SWBLI) characterized by large-scale, self-sustained periodic shock oscillations. On fan blades, the resulting unsteady aerodynamic loads from the low-frequency shock motion can couple with structural vibration modes, posing risks of potential structural failure. Hence, understanding the onset of buffet and its behaviours is vital for safe and reliable fan operation.

Extensive research on transonic buffet has been conducted on

isolated aerofoils and wings, providing a foundational understanding of the phenomenon. Early experimental studies identified buffet as a low-frequency shock oscillation, accompanied by periodic boundary layer separation and reattachment [1]. Numerical investigations employing unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (URANS) simulations have successfully captured buffet dynamics [2, 3]. More advanced methods, such as Large Eddy Simulation (LES) and Detached Eddy Simulation (DES), have provided deeper insights into the turbulent flow structures involved in buffet [4–6].

The underlying mechanism was hypothesized to be a feedback loop between downstream-travelling pressure waves generated by shock oscillations and upstream-propagating acoustic waves near the leading edge or trailing edge, sustaining shock movement [7]. On the other hand, global stability analysis linked buffet onset to the existence of an unstable global mode [8], the feedback loop can be interpreted as the physical process underpinning the emergence of the global instability. It is important to note that blade structural motion, as in flutter, does not contribute to the buffet mechanism, and the unsteadiness observed in these cases arises solely from aerodynamic effects.

Compared to external aerodynamics, transonic buffet in turbomachinery is less studied. Recent experimental investigations in compressor cascades have revealed shock oscillations associated with unsteady separation and SWBLI, suggesting the presence of a feedback loop mechanism analogous to that observed on aerofoils [9]. Both experimental and numerical investigations of the transonic compressor cascade TEAMAero [10] further demonstrated that the shock oscillation mechanism involves the propagation of pressure and acoustic waves within the blade passage. These waves interact strongly with the shock, leading to substantial variations in the local inflow angle and operating conditions [10]. In the context of fan blades, Becker et al. numerically studied unsteady shock behaviour on a BR710 fan blade at low Reynolds numbers and high altitudes, observing shock-induced unsteady separation [11]. Similarly, di Mare et al. examined shock-induced laminar-turbulent transition and unsteady shock movement on a transonic fan, highlighting the importance of shock dynamics in high-speed operation [12]. Majhi and Venkatraman identified feedback loops between upstream and downstream propagating pressure waves on NASA Rotor 67, reinforcing the connection between wave dynamics and shock unsteadiness on fan blades [13]. These studies, while limited, suggest that transonic buffet in turbomachinery shares similar fundamental physical mechanisms with external aerodynamics but its behaviour is further complicated by three-dimensional effects, and variable operating conditions.

In this work, the onset and characteristics of transonic buffet in a civil fan blade are investigated using time-accurate unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (URANS) simulations. The study is motivated by engine development tests, during which vibrations in the first flap mode (1F) were observed at some high-

speed operating conditions. The unsteady pressure and strain gauge signals were distinct from flutter responses. Given the high pre-shock Mach number ($Ma_{pre-shock} = 1.6$), SWBLI—namely transonic buffet—was identified as a likely root cause.

The aim of this paper is to identify the onset of shock buffet across the fan operating map and to analyse the associated shock dynamics under various operating conditions. The focus is placed on uncovering possible aerodynamic origin of transonic buffet within the fan stage, without considering any blade motion. Detailed investigations of shock oscillation frequencies and unsteady pressure fields around the blade surface are presented. These analyses offer new insights into the mechanisms driving buffet onset in civil fan blades and highlight its potential implications for future aerodynamic design and stability assessment.

2 METHODOLOGY

This section presents the flow solver and the numerical methods employed in the study. The test case setup is then described in detail, including the operating conditions, computational domain, and mesh resolutions.

2.1 Flow Solver

All simulations presented in this paper are conducted with the in-house steady and unsteady RANS solver AU3D. AU3D has been developed and validated over the past decades through collaboration between Imperial College London and Rolls-Royce. Its capability to accurately capture transonic separated flows and fluid–structure interactions in fans and compressors has been established in previous studies [14–16]. More specifically, the solver’s capability and accuracy in predicting transonic buffet has been validated against a benchmark aerofoil case [17]. AU3D is a finite volume flow solver that numerically solves the three-dimensional compressible RANS equations. The solver operates on a generic unstructured grid, with all flow variables discretised at the nodes. Numerical fluxes across cell interfaces are computed using Roe’s flux difference splitting scheme [18], in combination with the Jameson–Schmidt–Turkel (JST) dissipation scheme [19]. The solution algorithm is fully implicit and achieves second-order accuracy in both space and time. All simulations in this study employ the one-equation Spalart–Allmaras (SA) turbulence model [20] to provide closure to the RANS equations. Wall functions are used to model the boundary layers.

2.2 Test Case

The test case considered in this study is a transonic civil fan blade operating at high-speed off-design conditions, where blade vibrations were recorded during engine testing. The Reynolds number, based on the mid-span chord length, is 5.3×10^6 . The computational domain for both steady (RANS) and unsteady

(URANS) simulations consists of a single blade passage with circumferentially periodic boundaries. As illustrated in Fig. 1, the domain includes a straight inlet duct, the fan blade, a splitter section separating the core and bypass flows, and an empty bypass duct. A constant tip clearance of 0.2% span is modelled between the blade tip and the casing. Downstream of the by-

FIGURE 1: SKETCH OF THE SINGLE-PASSAGE COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN.

pass duct, a convergent–divergent nozzle is included to control the bypass mass flow via the nozzle throat area. The core mass flow is controlled through a prescribed mass flow function at the core exit boundary. At the inlet boundary conditions, we assume a uniform radial profile with a total temperature of 292 K and a total pressure of 100,813 Pa to match experimental conditions. The single-passage mesh comprises approximately 3×10^6 nodes, with an average wall $y^+ \approx 30$ on the blade surface. To reduce the complexity of the system and computational cost, Engine Section Stators (ESS) and Outlet Guide Vanes (OGV) are omitted from the domain. The mesh resolution and setup are consistent with prior validation work on transonic buffet using AU3D [17].

3 TRANSONIC BUFFET ONSET

To investigate the onset of transonic buffet for the fan blade, a series of steady and unsteady RANS simulations were performed across a range of operating conditions on the fan characteristic map. As shown in Fig. 2, multiple operating conditions were tested along four constant-speed lines, ranging from 99.8% to 104% aerodynamic speed. Both mass flow and total pressure ratio were normalised using the corresponding values from the design point. These operating points span from near-design conditions to high-speed off-design regions, where buffet-like phenomena were suspected based on engine test observations. Each unsteady simulation was initialised from a converged steady solution, followed by unsteady computations to resolve any time-dependent flow features. The nozzle exit area was systematically varied to map out the fan operating characteristics, with time-averaged inlet/outlet pressures and mass flows rates used to obtain each point on the characteristics.

In Fig. 2, each operating point is marked with a colour-coded marker, providing a qualitative classification of the flow

FIGURE 2: FAN CHARACTERISTIC MAP AT VARIOUS SPEED LINES.

unsteadiness based on shock movement behaviour and frequency content. Green indicates operating conditions where the shock remains steady, with no significant unsteady motion observed. Orange corresponds to cases with high-frequency oscillations, primarily originating from the wake and vortex shedding downstream of the shock. In these cases, the shock remains mostly stationary, and no large-scale separation or low-frequency shock motion is observed. Red identifies points where clear evidence of transonic buffet is found. These cases exhibit periodic, self-sustained oscillations of the shock, accompanied by unsteady boundary layer separation and strong surface pressure fluctuations at low frequencies. A transient operating point at these conditions orbits around the points in Fig. 2.

Across all three speed lines beyond the design speed, a consistent trend emerges: the onset of buffet occurs as the operating point approaches the choked end of the fan characteristic. This trend aligns with experimental observations. In this region, the fan operates at high mass flow rates and reduced back pressure, leading to larger pre-shock Mach numbers and stronger shock structures on the suction side of the blade where shock is also more swallowed into the passage. The shift from green to orange, and finally to red markers, reflects a progressive transition in flow behaviour—from steady shock, to high-frequency wake unsteadiness, and ultimately to low-frequency shock buffet. These flow behaviours and their implications will be examined in further detail in Section 4 for three operating point, OP1, OP2 and OP3, indicated in Fig. 2 on the 101% and 102.5% speed lines.

Fig. 3 presents snapshots of the pressure coefficient, $C_p = \frac{p - p_\infty}{\frac{1}{2} \rho_\infty U_\infty^2}$, on the blade suction side at buffet-onset condition OP2. The red line indicates the time-averaged shock position. The results show that the largest shock motion occurs near mid-span. To focus on the primarily two-dimensional shock buffet behaviour, further analysis is therefore conducted at 47% span, where the shock movement is most significant.

FIGURE 3: SNAPSHOTS OF PRESSURE COEFFICIENT CONTOUR ON THE BLADE SUCTION SIDE DURING ONE BUFFET CYCLE AT OP2. RED LINE INDICATES THE TIME-AVERAGED SHOCK LOCATION.

FIGURE 4: BLADE FORCE FREQUENCY SPECTRUM FROM FOURIER TRANSFORM AT 101% AERODYNAMIC SPEED OP1. NORMALISED BY THE MAXIMUM FORCE VALUE AT OP3

4 ANALYSIS OF SHOCK MOVEMENT AT DIFFERENT OPERATING CONDITIONS

At certain operating conditions before the buffet onset, significant high-frequency fluctuations are observed downstream in the blade wake region, although the shock remains largely stationary. To determine the frequency of this unsteadiness, the unsteady force on the blade in a direction normal to the blade chord is recorded over time.

4.1 High-frequency oscillations in the wake (OP1)

In this section, the unsteady wake behaviour is analysed at OP1.

A high-frequency response at 1010 Hz is observed in the force spectrum on the blade surface, as shown in Fig. 4. However, the associated amplitude is relatively small, indicating that this frequency is unlikely to originate from shock motion. This interpretation is further supported by both qualitative analysis of the flow field and quantitative examination of the surface pressure distribution, neither of which show evidence of large-scale unsteady shock behaviour at this frequency. To visualise small changes in the flow field, unsteady pressure coefficient $C'_p = \frac{p - \bar{p}}{p_{0,\infty} - p_\infty}$ is plotted, where \bar{p} is the time-averaged pressure field, $p_{0,\infty}$ is the free-stream (inlet) total pressure and p_∞ is the free-stream static pressure.

The unsteady pressure coefficient, shown in Fig. 5 for two different time steps across one period of the unsteadiness, reveals that the pressure perturbation originates from the trailing edge, as vortices are shed into the wake, and travels upstream towards the shock, where they are attenuated. These small-scale disturbances are responsible for the high-frequency response at 1010 Hz identified in the force spectrum. Although their amplitude is relatively low and they are not directly linked to large-scale shock motion, their presence indicates a persistent wake-induced unsteadiness in the flow. While the exact role of these wake-induced pressure waves in the development of buffet remains unclear, they may influence how large-scale shock oscillations are triggered.

4.2 Shock buffet (OP2 and OP3)

As the operating condition moves towards choke and the shock strengthens, the flow exhibits large-scale, low-frequency oscillations of transonic buffet. These oscillations are marked by

FIGURE 5: SNAPSHOTS OF UNSTEADY PRESSURE COEFFICIENT CONTOUR AT 47% SPAN DURING ONE HIGH-FREQUENCY CYCLE AT OP1.

periodic shock motion and associated boundary layer separation on the suction surface, especially around mid-span. This section examines and compares the aerodynamic features of buffet at two representative operating points, OP2 and OP3, focusing on surface pressure distribution and dominant buffet frequency.

4.2.1 OP2 Fig. 6 presents four instantaneous snapshots of the relative Mach number and corresponding negative axial velocity contours at 47% span, capturing the unsteady shock motion during a buffet cycle. The black line indicates the time-averaged shock position. Shock structure and its movement are firstly analysed from the relative Mach number snapshots, and the adverse velocity contours are then used to give more details on the SWBLI. From Fig. 6a 6b 6c 6d, the shock is fully swallowed within the blade passage and is located around 60% of the blade chord. At this position, the shock foot is distorted by its interaction with the thickened boundary layer, indicating localised separation and unsteady flow features. As illustrated in Figs. 6e to 6h, the negative axial velocity contours highlight the evolution of shock-induced separation throughout the buffet cycle. As the shock moves downstream from $t = 1T/4$ to $3T/4$, the size of the separated region behind the shock decreases, indicating partial boundary layer reattachment. Conversely, as the shock moves upstream from $t = 3T/4$ to $4T/4$ and back to $t = 1T/4$, the separation region grows rapidly. During this phase, the separated shear layers start to roll up into large vortical structures near the trailing edge, driven by the strong velocity gradient between the free-stream flow and the separated flow.

To further examine the shock motion, the surface pressure coefficient C_p is plotted at four time instances throughout a buffet cycle in Fig. 7. On the suction side, the shock traverses approxi-

mately 9% of the chord, oscillating between 0.55c and 0.64c. It also extends across the blade passage and interacts weakly with the pressure surface of the adjacent blade, with this interaction occurring between 0.3c and 0.6c on the pressure side.

Another important parameter for the shock motion is the buffet frequency, Fig. 8 shows the frequency spectrum of the unsteady force acting on the fan blade. A Fast Fourier Transform was used to extract the frequency contents from the time history of force over 0.3s (35 buffet cycles), where the initial transient was removed. A distinct peak is observed at 117 Hz, which corresponds to the fundamental buffet frequency identified from surface pressure and flow field analysis.

4.2.2 OP3 The characteristics of shock buffet are assessed under different conditions, where similar self-sustained periodic shock movement was observed as in OP2. Similar analysis to the one above is now conducted at OP3, which lies at a higher speed line. Figure 9 shows C_p distribution around the blade surface at 47% span, extracted at four time instants over one buffet cycle. The unsteady shock motion remains evident, with the shock foot now oscillating 12%c between approximately 0.55c and 0.67c, slightly wider in range compared to OP2. Similar to OP2, the shock extends across the blade passage and weakly interacts with the pressure surface of the adjacent blade, spans between 0.35c to 0.65c. The pressure distributions on both sides of the blade indicate the shock is more swallowed into the passage at OP3.

In Fig. 10, the blade force frequency spectrum shows a dominant peak at 107 Hz, which is lower than the 117 Hz observed at OP2. The difference in frequency is linked to the underlying acoustic feedback model, which is explained in Section 5.2.

5 MECHANISM OF BUFFET

To understand the underlying physics behind the onset and development of transonic buffet in the fan blade, this section examines the unsteady flow behaviour observed under buffet condition OP2. Particular attention is given to the role of back pressure variation, and the propagating disturbances which interact with the shock wave. These features are analysed in detail to assess possible feedback mechanism involving upstream and downstream propagating pressure or acoustic waves, which is responsible for sustaining the observed periodic shock oscillations.

5.1 Back pressure variation

In addition to Fig. 6, Fig. 11 presents the unsteady pressure variation at 47% span, visualised using unsteady pressure coefficient C'_p . These snapshots highlight the evolution of the pressure field downstream of the shock over a buffet cycle. At $t = 1T/4$, the shock is located at its most upstream position and there is a

FIGURE 6: SNAPSHOTS OF INSTANTANEOUS RELATIVE MACH NUMBER AND NEGATIVE AXIAL VELOCITY CONTOURS AT 47% SPAN DURING ONE BUFFET CYCLE AT OP2. BLACK LINES INDICATE THE TIME-AVERAGED SHOCK POSITION. THE AXIAL VELOCITY IS NORMALISED BY ITS MAXIMUM VALUE.

large separation zone downstream of the shock (6), which reduces the effective passage area. As a result, the back pressure in Fig. 11 is at its minimum value. As the shock moves downstream from $t = 1T/4$ to $t = 3T/4$, the back pressure gradually build up behind the shock as the separation zone shrinks. The maximum back pressure occurs when the shock reaches its most downstream location at $t = 3T/4$, where the separation zone is smallest. Following this, as the shock begins to move upstream from $t = 3T/4$ to $4T/4$, the back pressure decreases, and returns to its initial level at $t = 1T/4$. This cyclic variation in pressure is characteristic of transonic buffet and demonstrates the coupling between shock motion and pressure field downstream of the shock. Similar behaviour has been reported in the TCTA compressor cascade by López et al. [10], where such pressure fluctuations were attributed to a feedback loop involving upstream- and downstream-propagating disturbances that sustain the oscillatory shock motion.

5.2 Cross correlation of pressure fluctuation

To link the unsteady pressure perturbations described above to the buffet frequency, propagation velocities of the pressure perturbation and length scales of the passage geometry must be determined. Propagation velocities of the pressure perturbation can be determined from the correlation coefficient of near-wall pressure fluctuations on both sides of the blade surface [1]. The correlation coefficient $R_{nm}(\tau)$ is defined as

$$R_{nm}(\tau) = \frac{\overline{p'_n(t)p'_m(t+\tau)}}{\sqrt{\overline{p'^2_n}\overline{p'^2_m}}} \quad (1)$$

where two pressure fluctuation signals, $p'_n(t)$ and $p'_m(t+\tau)$, are measured at axial locations x_n and x_m along the blade surface, with a time delay τ . The location x_n is chosen as a fixed reference point upstream of the shock foot at $0.25c$, while x_m varies

FIGURE 7: NORMALISED SURFACE PRESSURE COEFFICIENT DISTRIBUTIONS OVER ONE BUFFET CYCLE AT 101% AERODYNAMIC SPEED OP2.

FIGURE 9: NORMALISED SURFACE PRESSURE COEFFICIENT DISTRIBUTIONS OVER ONE BUFFET CYCLE AT 102.5% AERODYNAMIC SPEED OP3.

FIGURE 8: BLADE FORCE FREQUENCY SPECTRUM FROM FOURIER TRANSFORM AT 101% AERODYNAMIC SPEED OP2. NORMALISED BY THE MAXIMUM FORCE VALUE AT OP3

FIGURE 10: BLADE FORCE FREQUENCY SPECTRUM FROM FOURIER TRANSFORM AT 102.5% AERODYNAMIC SPEED OP3. NORMALISED BY THE MAXIMUM FORCE VALUE AT OP3

along the chord. To isolate the components associated with the low-frequency shock oscillation at 117 Hz, the pressure signals p'_n and p'_m are band-pass filtered between 110-120 Hz for OP2, and 100-110 Hz for OP3. The resulting correlation coefficient for OP2 is plotted in Fig. 12. Only axial positions downstream of the shock at 60% chord are shown. The wave propagation speeds on the suction and pressure sides are then estimated from the gradient of a linear least-squares fit through the correlation maxima together with its propagation direction. As illustrated in Fig. 12, the pressure fluctuations behind the shock propagates downstream on the suction side with a velocity of $80c \text{ ms}^{-1}$. On the pressure side, acoustic waves travel upstream from the trailing edge at velocity of $200c \text{ ms}^{-1}$. It is important to note that the downstream-propagating wave speed was extracted in the region

0.8c to 1.0c from Fig. 12a. In contrast, the signals between 0.6c and 0.8c exhibit an instantaneous response. Combined with the evidence from Fig. 6 and 7, this region lies within the lambda shock structure and is strongly influenced by the unsteady shock motion, which alters the observed propagation speed.

5.3 Acoustic feedback model

Based on Lee's feedback model [7], the velocities identified above can be related to the buffet frequency. The model assumes that perturbations originating from the shock foot propagate downstream along the suction side and create pressure waves at the trailing edge which travel upstream towards the shock. The schematic illustration of these wave propagation

FIGURE 11: SNAPSHOTS OF UNSTEADY PRESSURE COEFFICIENT CONTOUR AT 47% SPAN DURING ONE BUFFET CYCLE AT OP2.

FIGURE 12: SPATIAL-TEMPORAL CORRELATIONS OF THE PRESSURE FLUCTUATIONS ON BOTH THE SUCTION SIDE AND PRESSURE SIDE AT 47% SPAN, 101% AERODYNAMIC SPEED OP2.

paths is shown in Fig. 13. The shock buffet frequency f_b can then be approximated by:

$$f_b = \left(\frac{l_d}{v_d} + \frac{l_u}{|v_u|} \right)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

where l_d is the distance travelled by the pressure wave from the shock foot to the trailing edge, v_d represents its downstream propagation speed. Likewise, l_u is the distance covered by the upstream-travelling acoustic wave from the trailing edge back to the shock, with v_u denoting its propagation speed. In Lee's original model [7], l_u was assumed to be equal to l_d . However, considering the circular propagation of acoustic waves, Hartmann et al. [21] and Majhi et al. [13] argued that the characteristic distance of travel for the upstream-propagating wave should instead be taken as the distance from the trailing edge to the upper end of the shock wave. In this case, the downstream and up-

FIGURE 13: THE FEEDBACK MODEL EXPLAINED ON AN AVERAGED RELATIVE MACH NUMBER FLOW FIELD AROUND THE BLADE AT 47% SPAN HEIGHT.

stream wave propagation speeds as determined from the cross-correlation above are $v_d = 80c \text{ ms}^{-1}$ and $v_u = -200c \text{ ms}^{-1}$, respectively. The value of v_u is very close to $(1 - Ma_{inlet})a = 222c \text{ ms}^{-1}$, where a is the local speed of sound and Ma_{inlet} is the relative inlet Mach number [22,23]. This agreement confirms that the dominant contribution to the pressure perturbation tracked on the pressure side in Fig. 12 is an acoustic wave. Using these values,

along with measured distances along the blade surface and inter-passage regions, the resulting buffet frequency predicted by this feedback model is 119 Hz at OP2. This prediction shows good agreement with the frequency 117 Hz obtained from the blade force time history. Similar analysis is done at OP3, where the propagation speeds from the correlations are $v_d = 80c \text{ ms}^{-1}$ and $v_u = -160c \text{ ms}^{-1}$. The predicted buffet frequency 108 Hz also matches well with 107 Hz calculated from blade force.

6 CONCLUSION

This study investigates the onset and underlying mechanisms of transonic shock buffet in a civil fan blade at high-speed off-design conditions. By examining a range of operating conditions on the fan characteristic map, buffet onset is clearly identified towards the choke side across multiple speed lines, consistent with experimental observations. Self-sustained periodic shock movement is encountered around the design speed of the fan at flow rates greater than those for peak efficiency or for which the fan was designed. A qualitative classification of unsteadiness reveals a transition from stationary shock to high-frequency wake oscillations and eventually to self-sustained, low-frequency shock buffet.

Prior to buffet onset, high-frequency wake-induced pressure waves are observed to propagate upstream towards the shock immediately prior to buffet onset. While their direct role in initiating shock motion remains unclear, their presence may influence the overall flow stability and interact with other disturbances, contributing to the emergence of low-frequency shock oscillations.

At buffet conditions, detailed analysis of the unsteady aerodynamics confirmed characteristic buffet features, including periodic shock oscillations, boundary layer separation and reattachment, and strong surface pressure fluctuations. The extent of shock movement spans approximately 10% of the chord. A wave-propagation-based feedback model, originally developed for isolated aerofoils [7], is adapted here for the fan blade scenarios. In this mechanism, a downstream-travelling pressure disturbance generated at the shock foot propagates along the suction surface and, upon reaching the trailing edge, is reflected upstream as an acoustic wave. This upstream-travelling disturbance interacts with the upper end of the shock, imparting energy that sustains its oscillatory motion and closes the feedback loop.

For the present transonic civil fan blade, the buffet frequencies predicted using this model match those identified from the fan forcing spectrum very well. This not only confirmed the role of upstream and downstream travelling pressure disturbances in buffet mechanism but also presents an encouraging step towards the approximation of buffet frequencies based on steady state simulations, which would significantly reduce the computational expense of buffet predictions in turbomachinery.

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